

ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON/EPOXY SAMPLES UNDER SHEAR FATIGUE LOADING

M. May, S.R. Hallett

Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science, University of Bristol
Queens Building, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, United Kingdom
Michael.May@bristol.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Short Beam Shear tests have been performed on IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy laminates for different stress levels and R-ratios. Progressive damage evolution was observed. Computer tomography examinations of externally undamaged samples revealed extensive internal cracking. A study of the R-ratio effect showed an increasing fatigue life for an increasing R-ratio (for constant maximum stress).

Keywords: Fatigue, experimental methods, shear testing

INTRODUCTION

The work presented in this paper is part of a larger test programme aiming at the experimental identification of damage onset in carbon/epoxy composites subject to fatigue loading allowing the calibration of novel numerical models for fatigue damage initiation [1]. Shear testing of composite materials is a complex task as it is very difficult to obtain a state of pure shear stress. Lessard [2] gives a comprehensive overview over different methods. Achieving an undesirable mixed mode I/II stress state is a very common problem. For this work an additional requirements for the calibration test are a cheap and easy manufacturing process and simple test procedure. With respect to the objective to identify damage initiation during cyclic loading it is not feasible to conduct tests with a predefined crack as they would only allow monitoring of progressive crack growth (propagation). An example of a simple test without any artificial defect is the Short Beam Shear test as described in ASTM D2344 [3]. Short Beam Shear tests provide shear strength data but do not provide stiffness information. A very short beam is tested in a three-point bending configuration. Assuming linear elastic properties, the stress distribution in this configuration features a linear axial stress distribution through the thickness of the beam with maximum compression under the loading roller, zero at the middle plane and maximum tension at the back surface. Additionally, there is a parabolic shear stress distribution (zero at tensile and compressive face, maximum in the middle plane), shown schematically in figure 1. There is also some through-thickness compression near the loading and support rollers which would tend to inhibit shear failure (not shown in figure 1). The superposition of these two stresses results in a state of pure shear in the middle plane of the sample away from the rollers and therefore the sample should fail in shear.

Figure 1: Stress distribution in Short Beam Shear tests

The Short Beam Shear test has been well characterised for static loads, but the amount of fatigue data available in the open literature is very little. The focus of this paper is to identify the driving damage mechanisms under fatigue loading. Real aerospace components are subject to a spectrum of different R-ratios during service life. The fatigue life for these components cannot be accurately predicted knowing only one baseline R-ratio. This paper therefore also investigates the effect of variable R-ratio on the onset of damage and final failure in Short Beam Shear specimens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The material chosen for this investigation is IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepreg. All specimens were cut from the same panel using a diamond saw and ground using 240Grit sandpaper. The panel consisted of 20 plies of unidirectional prepreg tape. A peel-ply was added on top and bottom of the prepreg during the vacuum bagging process to ensure a consistently good surface quality. The panel was cured in an autoclave using the manufacturer's recommended curing cycle. The average panel thickness after the autoclaving process was 2.55mm, corresponding to an average ply thickness of 0.1275mm.

Experimental Setup

The three-point bending rig was mounted in an INSTRON 8800 MJ 6272 servo-hydraulic test machine. The span between the support rollers is 12.7mm ($\frac{1}{2}$ "). Therefore the span/thickness ratio for the samples is about 5. The diameter of the loading roller is 6mm. This is larger than the standard and therefore avoids compressive failure underneath the roller. [4]

Figure 2: Test setup

Experimental Procedure

For static loading, the tests were run in displacement control with a test speed of 0.5mm/min. Tests were stopped at the first major load drop.

Fatigue tests have been performed under load control, initially setting the ratio of minimum to maximum stress per load cycle to $R = 0.1$. The severity was defined by the ratio of the applied stress to the mean value of the static strength. Tests were carried out for severities of 90%, 80%, 70% and 60%. Tests were stopped when the specimen failed catastrophically or the maximum displacement per load cycle had changed by more than 20%. Tests were also stopped when 10^7 cycles had been exceeded. After having finished the test programme for $R = 0.1$, additional tests have been performed using $R = 0.5$ for further investigation of some of the effects found for $R = 0.1$ and to assess the effect of R-ratio.

The damage in specimens that yielded the maximum displacement-criterion has been assessed using a Micro Computed Tomography (CT) X-Ray system, SKYSCAN 1174, allowing a revelation of the internal structure of the sample. The sample is rotated at a given angular speed and X-ray-images are taken at regular intervals. Algorithms allow comparison of the images for different angles and construction of a 3D model of the internal structure. Virtual section cuts can then be made at any arbitrary angle through the model.

In an additional step, the CT scanner was used for regular inspections of two samples which were both loaded at 87.5% of the static value and $R = 0.5$.

RESULTS

Under fatigue loading the specimens did not show any visible sign of damage on the edges before they failed catastrophically or before the maximum displacement criterion was met. Catastrophic failure was observed for high levels of applied stress while most of the tests run at lower levels of stress were stopped when the maximum displacement criterion was met. Fig. 3 shows sample B35 which failed catastrophically. It can be seen several delaminations have formed extending from one edge to the centre of the

specimen. It can also be seen that compressive failure has occurred under the location of the loading roller.

Figure 3: Sample after failure (loading was on top surface)

The steadily increasing maximum displacement shown in Fig. 4 would seem to indicate that some damage is growing inside the specimen but has not yet reached the edges. CT scans were taken at regular intervals during the fatigue loading to support this hypothesis. There were some concerns that the compressive failure under the roller was driving the shear failure. A PHOTRON APX RS high speed digital video camera was therefore used to monitor the sequence of events at failure.

Figure 4: Typical stiffness plot based on crosshead-readings for maximum displacement

Sequence of damage events

The same sample (B35) was inspected by CT scanning prior the first load cycle, after 50 cycles, 100 cycles and 250 cycles. The CT scan before the first load cycle did not show any sign of damage throughout the specimen. The first interval scan after 50 full load cycles also did not reveal any delamination damage as shown in Fig.5a) and 5d).

Figure 5: CT scans of sample B35 at different stages of fatigue life, a)-c) are 9.5mm from end, d)-f) are 11.4mm from end. The damage has been enhanced visually.

A CT scan after 100 full load cycles revealed a delamination between the 5th and 6th ply from top, near the point of loading (see Fig. 5b and 5e). The size of the delamination is approximately 2.5mm in width and 2.1mm in length. The delamination was close to the edge of the sample but did not fully extend to it, so it was not detectable using optical techniques. The lower bound for the initiation time is 50 cycles, the upper bound is 100 cycles. The cyclic loading was continued to assess the propagation of damage. The next scan was carried out after 250 full load cycles. It was observed that the crack did not propagate much in specimen length direction, but multiple cracks appeared across the full width. Cycling was continued until the sample failed catastrophically after 255 full load cycles.

Sample 36 was inspected prior the first load cycle, after 10 cycles, 100 cycles, 250 cycles, 500 cycles, 750 cycles and 850 cycles.

Figure 6: CT scans of sample B36 at different stages of fatigue life, a)-c) are 16.4mm from end, d)-f) are 14.7mm from end, g)-i) are 12.8mm from end. The damage has been enhanced visually.

The CT scans before the first load cycle, after 10 cycles, 100 cycles, 250 cycles and 250 cycles did not reveal any sign of delamination inside the specimen. Three section cuts are shown in Fig. 6. The following CT scan, after 750 cycles, revealed a large crack near the centre of the specimen. It was about 3.6mm in length with a variable width, extending nearly the whole sample width for a section at 14.7mm from the end (see Fig. 6e). Similar to the previous sample, there were no external signs of damage on the specimen. The point of damage initiation is bounded between 500 cycles and 750 cycles. A final scan was conducted after 850 full load cycles and similar to the previous sample it was observed that the crack had grown significantly in width direction, but only a small amount in the length direction.

None of the CT scans gave insight into the formation and coalescence of micro cracks prior to the formation of macroscopic delaminations. The reason for this is that the sample was not under load during the CT scans and the micro-cracks had closed up and could not be detected with the given resolution of 18 micron.

The high speed camera images revealed that the compressive failure of the samples occurred after the formation of the delamination. CT scans also did not show any evidence of interaction between through-thickness compression and delamination

Identification of damage onset

In a further step it was investigated if the point of initiation can be found using the change in the variation of displacement ($d_{\max} - d_{\min}$) in each load cycle. The maximum and minimum displacements in each load cycle have been extracted from the output files generated by the test machine using an in-house software tool. The “apparent stiffness change” which contains change due to the experimental setup and real stiffness change due to cracking is defined as the ratio of the initial displacement at $N=1$ to the current displacement. Fig. 7 illustrates the apparent stiffness change for sample 35.

Figure 7: Apparent stiffness change vs. Cycles for sample 35

Initially, the stiffness seems to be increasing, which is a problem inherent to the test setup. A possible explanation for this phenomenon is wear under the roller spreading the load and reducing the localised displacement due to indentation. The collected data can therefore not be used to describe the actual amount of stiffness change. However, it can be seen that the slope of the curve changes significantly after 83 cycles. This indicates that some major damage has occurred. Recalling the results from the CT scans for this same specimen, indicating that the initiation has occurred between cycles 50 and 100, the drastic change of the slope can be used as an indicator of damage onset. The same analysis was carried out for sample 36 for which the CT scans revealed that the damage onset was between cycles 500 and 750. Fig. 8 illustrates the apparent stiffness change for sample 36.

Figure 8: Apparent stiffness change vs. Cycles for sample 36

Once again, the stiffness seems to be gradually increasing, thought to be due to wear at the roller. A drastic change in slope of the curve can be seen after 556 cycles which lies within the bounds given by the CT scan results. The displacement change seems to be a suitable identifier for the onset of fatigue damage in Short Beam Shear specimens.

Analysis of R-ratio effect

Two different R-ratios have been investigated: $R=0.1$ and $R=0.5$. SN-curves for damage initiation have been generated for both R-ratios using the apparent stiffness change criterion proposed in the previous section. A comparison of both SN-curves can be seen in Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Comparison of SN-curves for initiation for different R-ratios

It can be seen that the SN-curve for R=0.5 is significantly flatter than the SN-curve for R=0.1. A similar trend was observed for the total fatigue life (defined by catastrophic failure or a 20% change in maximum displacement) as shown in Fig. 10. For high levels of stress, final failure occurs shortly after initiation of damage. For lower levels of cyclic stress the initiation phase is followed by a long propagation phase, resulting in a reduction of the gradient of the SN-curves compared to the SN-curves for initiation.

Figure 10: Comparison of SN-curves for life for different R-ratios

DISCUSSION

The damage mechanisms in Short Beam Shear samples under fatigue loading have been studied. Unlike the static case, the Short Beam Shear samples do not fail suddenly when loaded in fatigue. Under fatigue loading, the damage initiates locally and slowly propagates, initially across the width of the specimen and subsequently in length-direction. The onset location is in the vicinity of the loading roller but not directly underneath as the through-thickness compression inhibits shear failure. Once a macroscopic delamination has reached the end of the specimen, compressive failure occurs.

The onset of cracking can be determined indirectly by monitoring the change of relative displacements during cyclic loading. This is however not a very accurate technique and can only be seen as an indicator.

The initiation time plays a dominant role in fatigue life of SBS samples for high levels of cyclic stress. For lower levels of stress, the major part of fatigue life is dominated by slow propagation of an internal macro-crack.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Micro CT system SKYSCAN 1174 used was on loan from the EPSRC Instrument pool. This project has been funded by Great Western Research, Rolls-Royce Plc and Agusta Westland.

References

1. May M, Hallett SR. A robust Interface Element Formulation for the Simulation of Damage Initiation under Low Levels of Cyclic Stress, *2nd ECCOMAS Thematic Conference on Mechanical Response of Composites*, 1-3 April 2009, London, United Kingdom.
2. Lessard LB, Eilers OP and Shokrieh MM: Modification of the Three-Rail-Shear Test for Composite Materials under Static and Fatigue Loading, *Composite Materials Design and Testing 13, ASTM STP 1242*, 1997.
3. ASTM D 3846: Standard Test Method for In-Plane Shear Strength of Reinforced Plastics.
4. Cui WC and Wisnom MR. "Contact Finite Element Analysis of Three- and Four-Point Short-Beam Bending of Unidirectional Composites", *Composite Science and Technology 45*, pp.323-334, 1992.